

Reactions of 2-Arylazo-Naphthalene-1-Sulphenylbromide with "Carbon Acids": Synthesis of 2-Substituted Naphthothiazoles and their U. V. and I. R. Spectra

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2-n-Tolylazonaphthalene-1-sulphenylbromide (IIb) condenses with carbon acids of the type $Z\cdot CH_2\cdot Z$ where 'Z' is an acidifying keto-carbonyl group, to yield 2-substituted naphtho-2' : 1' : 4:5-thiazolyl compounds (III). 2-phenylazonaphthalene-1-sulphenylbromide (IIa) also reacts similarly. With weaker carbon acids e.g., acetone acetophenone, (IIb) reacts only under more stringent conditions, but (IIa) fails to react. The U. V. as well as I. R. spectra of the 2-substituted naphthothiazoles are presented.

IN an earlier publication Burawoy *et al*¹ observed that azo-benzene-2-sulphenyl bromide reacted with malonic acid to yield benzothiazolyl-2-carboxylic acid(I), together with aniline salt. Similar reactions of 2-arylazonaphthalene-1-sulphenylhalides have not been reported so far. We have now studied the reactions of 2-phenylazonaphthalene-1-sulphenyl bromide (IIa) and 2-*p*-tolylazonaphthalene-1-sulphenyl bromide (IIb) with compounds of the type $Z\cdot CH_2\cdot Z$, where 'Z' is an acidifying keto-carbonyl group. Thus both of these sulphenylbromides reacted with acetylacetone to yield -2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazolyl-2-methyl ketone (IIIa), with acetoacetic ester, malonic ester and cyanacetic ester to yield ethyl-naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazolyl-2-carboxylate (IIIb), with acetoacetanilide to yield anilide of naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazolyl-2-carboxylic acid (IIIc) and with malonic acid to yield naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazole (IIId). Aniline or *p*-toluidine hydrobromide was also isolated from the mother liquors.

2-Phenylazo-naphthalene-1-sulphenylbromide did not react with weaker carbon acid e.g. acetone and acetophenone even on long refluxing for over 100 hours in presence of 2 drops of conc. hydrochloric acid. 2-*p*-tolylazo-naphthalene-1-sulphenylbromide however reacted with acetone and acetophenone on prolonged refluxing with 2 drops of conc. hydrochloric acid to yield naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazolyl-2-methyl ketone (IIIa) and naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazolyl-2-phenyl ketone (IIIe) respectively. The formation of the heterocyclics may be assumed to take place as follows:—At first 2-arylazo-naphthalene-1-sulphenylbromide reacts with "carbon acids" to form the corresponding sulphides (1) with the elimination of hydrobromic acid. The azo-group of these sulphides gets protonated (2) and subsequently intramolecular five-membered hetero-ring closure takes place (3) by the action of protonated azo-group with the potential nucleophilic centre. These cyclized products get aromatized to 1 : 3-thiazole-derivatives (4) by partial ethanolysis accompanied with the elimination of an arylamine molecule.

(I)

(II)

a R=H
b R=CH₃

(III)

a, R=CH₃CO.
b, R=COOC₂H₅
c, R=CONHC₆H₅
d, R=H
e, R=C₆H₅CO.

(1)

(2)

(3)

(4)

***U-V spectra of 2-substituted naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazoles**

Like benzothiazoles and benzoxazoles², the first band system of naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazoles retain the vibrational structure of the benzo ring chromophore, only difference is that it suffers a bathochromic shift. It appeared around 325 nm (three peaks at 332 nm, 325 nm and 317 nm). The weak conjugation of the ring system with the heteroatoms would result in such a moderate bathochromic shift. The second band at 288 nm appears as a shoulder and the foot of it is implanted with the third band at shorter wavelength (at 288 nm). The intensities of these two bands at shorter wavelengths are higher than that of the longer wavelength band.

TABLE

COR	First band		Second band		Third band	
	λ (nm)	ϵ	λ (nm)	ϵ	λ (nm)	ϵ
R=H	332	1727				
	325	1364	302	4091	288	5727
	317	1273				
R=CH ₃	358	7900	315	8750	286	6830
R=C ₂ H ₅	359	8500	318	9251	288	8821
R=OEt	347	4640	314	10320	288	9600
R=NHPh	349	12879	318	20606	288	14424
R=C ₆ H ₅	372	2998	326	8650	286	9000

When 2-position of naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazole is substituted with a group-COR (where R=CH₃, C₂H₅, Ph-, OEt and NHPh), the effect is smoothening of the longer wavelength band (325 nm band) which loses its vibrational fine structure and is attended with a moderate bathochromic shift. As expected the bathochromic shift is the highest for the compound where R=Ph (the band appears at 372 nm) followed by the compound where R=CH₃ and C₂H₅ (at 358 nm and 359 nm respectively) and for the compounds where R=OEt or NHPh the band appears at 347 nm and 349 nm respectively.

The difference between the nature and position of these bands of naphthiazole and its above mentioned 2-substituted derivatives may be ascribed to the conjugation between C=O of the substituent and the C=N of the hetero ring.

The third band at shorter wavelength (i.e., the band at 288 nm) of naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazole practically remains unaffected by the 2-substituent.

* U. V.—Visible spectra were taken in DK-2 Spectrophotometer

** IR-Spectra were taken in Karl Zeiss Jena U. R.-10 infrared Spectrophotometer in KBr pellets.

But 2-substitution of naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazole ring brings a clear separation of the 302 nm band. This band in the 2-substituted naphthothiazoles, appears at slightly longer wavelength region (around 315 nm).

**** The I.R. Spectra of 2-substituted naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazoles**

The infra-red spectra of all these 2-substituted naphtho 2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazoles were taken in KBr pellets. Besides the carbonyl vibrations in the region 1750-1650 Cm⁻¹ (for the groups like -COOC₂H₅, CONHPh, -COCH₃ and -COC₂H₅), a pair of bands of medium intensity at 1470 cm⁻¹ and 1430 cm⁻¹ were found to be characteristic of all these compounds, including the unsubstituted naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazole. Thus this pair of bands may be identified to be characteristic of the structures like naphtho-2' : 1' : 4 : 5-thiazole. It was interesting to note that the carbonyl conjugation of the 2-substituents with hetero ring had practically no effect on these two bands.

Experimental

1. *Reaction with acetylacetone* : 0.5 g of (II, b) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and 1 ml of acetylacetone was added to it. The mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature till the reaction was complete (72 hrs). Yellow plates of (III, a) thus formed was filtered off, washed and dried (0.22 g, 68%). Recrystallization from ethanol gave light yellow plates, m.p. 179°-181°. (Found, C, 68.3; H, 4.1; N, 5.9. C₁₈H₉NSO requires C, 68.7; H, 4.0; N, 6.2%). *p*-Toluidine hydrobromide was recovered from the mother liquor.

(II, a) also reacted with acetylacetone under similar conditions to yield (III, a) in four days.

2. *Reaction with acetoacetic ester* : 0.5 g of (II, b) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and acetoacetic ester (1 ml) was added to it and allowed to stand at room temperature till the reaction was complete (6 days). The residue after removal of the solvent was recrystallized from ethanol whereby greenish-white crystals of (III, b) was obtained (0.26 g, 71%), m.p. 131°-133°. (Found, C, 65.6; H, 4.3; N, 5.3. C₁₄H₁₁NSO₂ requires C, 65.4; H, 4.3; N, 5.5%).

3. *Reaction with malonic ester* : 0.5 g (II, b) reacted with malonic ester according to the procedure as under (2) to give (III, b) in 9 days. Yield, 0.22 g (60%), m.p. & mixed m.p. 131-133°. (Found, C, 65.6; H, 4.5; N, 5.5. C₁₄H₁₁NSO₂ requires C, 65.4; H, 4.3; N, 5.5%). The mother liquor yielded *p*-toluidine hydrobromide.

(II, a) also reacted with malonic ester similarly to yield (III, b) in 12 days.

4. *Reaction with cyanacetic ester* : (II, b) reacted with cyanacetic ester according to the procedure as under (2) to yield (III, b) in five days with an yield of 60%, m.p. and mixed m.p. 131-133°. (Found, C, 65.5;

H, 4.4; N, 5.9. $C_{14}H_{11}NSO_2$ requires, C, 65.4; H, 4.3; N, 5.5%). From the mother liquor *p*-toluidine hydrobromide was obtained.

(II, a) also reacted with cyanacetic ester under similar experimental conditions to yield (III, b) in 6 days. The mother liquor yielded aniline hydrobromide.

5. *Reaction with acetoacetanilide*: 0.5 g of (II, b) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and acetoacetanilide (0.5 g) in ethanol (5 ml) was added to it. The reaction was complete in 24 hrs. The shining yellow precipitate of the anilide of naphtho-2':1' : 4:5-thiazole-2-carboxylic acid (III, c) was filtered off, washed and dried, (0.4 g, 90%). Recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 208-210°. (Found, C, 71.2; H, 4.1; N, 8.8. $C_{18}H_{12}N_2SO$ requires C, 71.1; H, 4.0; N, 9.2). The mother liquor contained *p*-toluidine hydrobromide. (II, a) also reacted with aceto-acetanilide under similar conditions to give (III, c). From the mother liquor aniline-hydrobromide was obtained.

6. *Reaction with malonic acid*: Malonic acid (0.5 g) in ethanol (5 ml) was added to a solution of II, b (0.5 g) in ethanol (25 ml) and the reaction was complete in 12 days, at room temperature. The solvent was evaporated off and was extracted with cold water (25 ml) and filtered. The residue (0.15 g, 60%) on recrystallization from aqueous ethanol gave colourless crystals of (III, d), m.p. 63-65°. (Found, C, 71.0; H, 4.1; N, 7.9. $C_{11}H_7NS$ requires C, 71.4; H, 3.8; N, 7.6). The water extract on evaporation gave *p*-toluidine hydrobromide. (II, a) reacted with malonic acid in 15 days under similar experimental procedure,

to yield (III, d). The mother liquor gave aniline hydrobromide on evaporation.

7. *Reaction with acetone at room temperature*: Acetone (3 ml) was added to a solution of (II, b) (0.5 g) in ethanol (25 ml) and the mixture was allowed to stand at room temperature till the reaction was complete (30 days). The resulting yellow plates of (III, a) was filtered, washed and dried (0.21 g, 67%). Recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 179-181°. (Found, C, 68.3; H, 4.2; N, 6.2. $C_{18}H_9NSO$ requires C, 68.7; H, 4.0; N, 6.2%).

8. *Reaction with acetone at high temperature*: A mixture of II, b (0.5 g) in ethanol (25 ml), acetone (3 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (2 drops) was refluxed (18 hrs), till the reaction was complete. The solution on cooling gave (III, a) which was filtered off, washed and dried, (0.2 g, 63%). Recrystallized from ethanol, m.p and mixed m.p. 179-181°.

9. *Reaction with acetophenone at high temperature*: A mixture of II, b (0.5 g), acetophenone (A. R., 3 ml) and conc. hydrochloric acid (2 drops) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed till the reaction was complete (50 hrs). The solution on cooling yielded III, e (0.3 g, 76%). Recrystallized from ethanol, m.p. 150-151°. (Found, C, 74.6; H, 4.2; N, 5.2. $C_{18}H_{11}NOS$ requires C, 74.7; H, 3.8; N, 4.9%).

References

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